

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Review Article

A Review on Formulation and Evaluation of Tetra herbal Hair Oil

Shital Sagale*, Rohit Jadhav, Archana Chavan, Dhananjay Khandebharad, Komal Matsagar

Oyster Institute of Pharmacy, Golatgaon, Chh. Sambhajinagar.

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 25 May 2025

Keywords:

Kalonji (Black seed),
Fenugreek seed Castor oil,
Chemical constituents,
Evaluation Hair Growth,
Prevent, Hair loss

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.15511498

ABSTRACT

In today's world, where everyone chooses instant effect mainly concern with health and cosmetic, but after a couple of days it gives major side effects that's why major group of peoples turning towards Herbal products which gives more effect and less side effects. Today's generation is facing for many health issues, also issues related to skin, hairs. So, the peoples from each generation whether men or women facing to hair problems like, Hair growth, split ends, hair baldness, Dandruff, Hair Loss, etc. These problems are due to Nutritional Deficiency, emotional & physical stress, changing lifestyle, genetic disorders. In body some hormonal imbalance and hormonal changes takes place that also effect on hair. Herbal cosmetic products have high demand for these issues because they have potential effect so that can be trustable. So, we here to show activity of KALONGI (Black seed) to treat Hair issues, one constituent of black seed named as, Thymoquinone is stated as powerful positive effect. Black seed also referred as miraculous herb which is gifted by our nature to us due to its medicinal potential and therapeutic values.

INTRODUCTION

The Hair has Protective Role against adverse effect of external factors. The individuals mainly disturbed due to common hair shaft disorders. Hair problems like, hair loss, baldness, split ends, dandruff, etc. In that reduction of Hair volume is dermatological disorder to prevent this hair loss to take care of hair proper treatment and Nutrient is required. Once, Prophet Mohammed said about

kalonji that, "There is healing in Black seed for all disease/disorder except death". Kalonji, its scientific name is *Nigella sativa*, belongs to the family Ranunculaceae. Its constituents are potential to fight Hair Fall & even induce Hair Growth presence of Nigellone & Thymoquinone. Also, a Fenugreek seed, used to treat hair loss due to its antioxidant property. fenugreek seed, scientifically known as *Trigonella foenum-graecum*, belongs to Family Fabaceae. Fenugreek

***Corresponding Author:** Shital Sagale

Address: *Oyster Institute of Pharmacy, Golatgaon, Chh. Sambhajinagar.*

Email ✉: shitalsagale921@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

seed rich source of Iron & Protein, Nicotinic acid that result in increased hair growth. Castor oil Help reduce spilt end and helpful for treatment of dandruff. Herbal hair oil is one of the most recognized Hair treatment Herbal Hair oils it not only moisturizes scalp but also reverse dry scalp & dry hair condition for that use Kalonji. It provides essential Nutrients. Nutrients required to maintain normal functions; sebaceous gland promote Natural hair growth. Formulation & Evaluation of Tetra herbal Hair oil containing herb like, Kalonji, Fenugreek Seed, Castor Oil & Coconut Oil. Evaluation of include organoleptic and chemical parameters.

Scientific Classification of Components:

Kalonji (*Nigella Sativa*):

Kingdom: Plantae

Clade: Tracheophytes

Clade: Angiosperms

Clade: Eudicots Order

Ranunculales Family : Ranunculaceae Genus, *Nigella* Species, *Nigella sativa*

Fig. No. 01: Kalonji Seed

Fenugreek Seed:

Kingdom: Plantae

Clade: Tracheophytes

Clade: Angiosperms

Clade: Eudicots

Clade: Rosids

Order: Fabales

Family: Fabaceae

Genus: *Trigonella* Species: *T. foenum-graecu*

Fig No.02 Fenugreek Seed

Castor Oil:

Kingdom: Plantae

Clade : Tracheophytes

Clade : Angiosperms

Clade : Eudicots

Clade : Rosids Order

: Malpighiales Family : Euphorbiaceae Subfamily : Acalyphoideae

Tribe: Acalyphea Subtribe: Riciniinae

Genus: *Ricinus* L. Species: *R. communis*

Fig.No.03: Castor Oil

Coconut Oil:

Kingdom: Plantae

Clade : Tracheophytes

Clade : Angiosperms

Clade : Monocots Clade

: Commelinids

Order: Arecales Family

: Arecaceae Subfamil

: Arecoideae Tribe

Fig.No.04: Coconut

Chemical Constitutents

- **Kalonji:**

Thymoquinone Thymol

d-citronellol

P- cymene

Str.No.05: Thymoquinone

Str.No.06: p-cymene

Fenugreek

Palmitic acid

Linoleic acid

Pinene

Str.No.03: Palmitic acid

Str.No.04: linoleic acid

- **Castor Oil**

Ricinoleic acid

Str.No.05: Ricinoleic acid

Oleic acid

Dihydroxy steric acid

Str.No.06: Oleic acid

- **Coconut Oil**

Caprylic acid

Str.No.07: Caprylic acid

Lauric acid

Myristic acid

Str.No.08: Myrist

MATERIAL AND METHOD

- **Collection Of Components:**

Kalonji Seed: Kalonji seed is collected from fruit of nigella sativa plant, during season of winter.

Fenugreek Seed: Fenugreek seed collected from pods of plant, which are fully ripened and collected before pod pops open.

Castor Oil: Oil is extracted by method solvent extraction, mechanical pressing or by combination of pressing and extraction.

Coconut Oil: Coconut oil is extracted from coconut kernel (fresh or copra) by using wet milling or dry milling method.

Hibiscus Flower: Hibiscus flower is collected from various regions, depending on the species.

And composed of several key parts; sepals, petals, stamens and the pistil.

Formulation Table:

Sr. No.	Ingredients	Quantity
---------	-------------	----------

1.	Kalonji seed (Black seed)	10gm
2.	Fenugreek seed	5gm
3.	Castor oil	15ml
4.	Coconut oil	20ml

Procedure Of Herbal Hair Oil

Take a given quantity of kalonji seed and fenugreek seed

make a powder of kalonji seed and then fenugreek seed separately by using grinding method.

Then mix both the powder.

Add this mixture of powder into a castor oil.

Then add given quantity of coconut oil into above mixture.

Transfer this mixture into a glass bottle.

Placed that glass bottle into a warm water for 2 hours and then keep it in a sunlight for a week.

Evaluation Of Herbal Hair Oil

The formulated Hair oil was Evaluated using organoleptic parameters and physicochemical

parameters like pH, Acid Value, Saponification Value, Refractive Index, viscosity.

- **Organoleptic parameters:**

In this test, color, Odour and skin irritation test are being observed. This test performs manually. Oil is applied on the hand and exposed it to sunlight. Result is observed by 5mins.

• **Physicochemical parameters:**

Acid Value-

10 ml Oil added 25 ml ethanol & 25 ml ether. Phenolphthalin used as indicator & titrated with 0.1M Potassium Hydroxide solution.

Acid value = $5.61n/w$

Saponification Value-

2g Oil weigh and transferred 250 ml Iodine flask 25 ml of 0.5M alcoholic Potassium hydroxide added then boiled under Reflex water bath for 30min phenolphthalin was used indicator titrated against 0.5M HCL.

Saponification value = $28.05(b-a)/w$

Where,

w=weight in gram of solution

pH-

pH check by using pH meter.

Viscosity-

It is determined by using Ostwalds Viscometer.

Specific gravity-

It is determined using Pyknometer or Specific gravity bottle.

Uses

Kalonji:

- Kalonji helps to hair to retain their pigment cells rather than losing pigments.
- It is used to induce hair regrowth due to presence of nigellone and thymoquinone.
- Kalonji nourishes the hair follicle and improve health of hair follicles.
- The regular use of kalonji resist hairs to turn into grey hairs.
- It contains high fatty acid which makes hair soft and moisturize.

Fenugreek:

- Fenugreek gives 2 essential nutrients, that are iron and protein.
- It has antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties that help to remove dandruff, prevent scalp irritation.
- Nicotinic acid helps to promote hair growth.
- Potassium prevents the premature grey hair.
- Lecithin keep hair nourishes and straightens.

Castor Oil:

- It is mainly used as a natural hair conditioner.
- It uses regular basis on hair helps to lubricate the hair shaft, increasing flexibility and decreasing the chance of breakage.
- castor oil moisturizes the hair and vitamin E rich compound.
- It has antibacterial properties for scalp health.
- Balance the pH levels and also boosts hair follicle health.

Coconut Oil:

- Coconut oil promoting hair growth.
- It has preventing baldness and grey hair.
- It helps to remove dandruff.
- It prevents hair loss, nourish and tones dry hair.
- Treated with scalp related problem.

Pharmacological activities are as following:

CONCLUSION

1. Formulation Efficacy: - The Tetra herbal Hair Oil formulation shows promise in terms of its effectiveness. Specific herbs and ingredients included in the formulation contribute positively to hair health, such as promoting growth, reducing dandruff, or improving scalp conditions.

2. Evaluation Parameters: - The evaluation criteria used in the review likely assessed various aspects such as physical characteristics (color, odor, viscosity), chemical composition (active ingredients), and biological effects (clinical trials or user feedback).

3. Effectiveness: - Depending on the study design, the effectiveness of Tetra herbal Hair Oil may have been validated through controlled experiments, user surveys, or comparative studies against existing commercial products.

4. Safety and Side Effects: - Evaluating any potential side effects or safety concerns associated with long-term use is crucial. Reviews typically discuss this aspect to ensure consumer safety and product reliability.

5. Recommendations: - Concluding recommendations are often based on the overall findings of the review. These may include suggestions for further research, improvements in formulation, or insights for consumer use.

REFERENCES

1. Ansari S.H. and Ali M. Hair care and herbal drug. Indian J Nat Prod. 13(1): 3-5, 1997.
2. Rathi V., Rathi J.C., Tamizharasi S. and Pathak A.K. Plants used for hair growth promotion: A review Phcog Rev. 2(3): 165-167,2008
3. Patni P., Varghese D., Balekar N. and Jain D.K. Formulation and evaluation of herbal hair oil for alopecia management. Planta Indica. 2(3): 27-30, 2006

4. Purwal, L., Gupta, S. B. N. and Pande, M.S. Development and Evaluation of Herbal Formulations for hair growth, *E- Journal of Chemistry*, Jan 2008, Vol- 5, NO-1, 34-38.
5. Bhatia SC. Perfumes, soaps, detergents and cosmetics. 2nd edn. New Delhi. CBS Publishers and distributors; 2001; 639, 641.
6. Mithal BM, Shah RN. A hand book of cosmetics. 1st edn. New Delhi. Vallabh prakashan; 2000; 141-142.
7. Kirtikar K.P. and Basu B.D., *Indian Medicinal Plants*, Vol I, International Book Distributors, Dehradun, 1995, 768-769.
8. Shah C S, Qudry J S, *A Text book of Pharmacognosy*, 11th Edn.,
9. B.S. Shah Prakashan, Ahmedabad, 1996; 119.
10. Evans W C, Trease and Evans. *Pharmacognosy*, 15th Ed., W.B. Saunders Harcourt Publishers Ltd., 2002; 292.
11. *The Aurvedic Formulary of India*, Government of India, Ministry of Health and family planning, Department of health, Delhi, 1st ed 1978; part 1, 99.
12. N. Sanju, N. Arun and K. K. Roop, *Cosmetic Technology*, 1st Edition, Birla Publications Pvt. Ltd, Delhi (2006) pp. 379-382.
13. Adhirajan, N., Dixit, V. K. and Chandrakasan, G., *Development and Evaluation of Herbal Formulations for Hair growth*, *Indian Drugs*, Nov-2001, 38 (11), 559-563.
14. Roy, R. K., Thakur, M., Dixit, V. K., *Development and Evaluation of polyherbal formulation for hair growth- promoting activity*, *Journal of Cosmetic Dermatology*, Nov-2006, 6, 108-112.
15. N. Sanju, N. Arun and K. K. Roop, *Cosmetic Technology*, 1st Edition, Birla Publications Pvt. Ltd, Delhi (2006) pp. 379-382.
16. S. Kaul and S. Dwivedi, *Indigeneous Ayurvedic Knowledge of Some Species in the Treatment of Human Disease and Disorders*, *Int. J. Pharm. Life Sci.*, 1(1), 44-49 (2010).
17. B. M. Mithal and R. N. Shah, *A Hand Book of Cosmetics*, 1st Edition, Vallabh Prakashan, Delhi (2000) pp. 141-142.
18. R. Shoba Rani Hiremath *Textbook of Industrial Pharmacy*, 1st Edition, Orient Longaman Pvt. Ltd., Hyderabad (2007) pp. 99-102.
19. S. C. Bhatia, *Perfumes, Soaps, Detergents and Cosmetics*, 2nd Edition, CBS Publishers and Distributions, Delhi (2001) pp. 639- 641. *Indian Pharmacopoeia*, Government of India, Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Published by, The Controller of Publication, Edition, Vol. II (1996).
20. Sharma P, Yelne M, Dennis T (2005) *Database on medicinal plants used in Ayurveda*. CCRAS New Delhi.
21. Tembhurne S, Feroz S, More B, Sakarkar DM (2014) *A review on therapeutic potential of Nigella sativa (kalonji) seeds*. *Medicinal plants research* 8(3): 167- 177.
22. Ahmad A, Husain A, Mujeeb M, Khan SA, Najmi A, et al. (2013) *A review on therapeutic potential of Nigella sativa: A miracle herb*. *Asian Pac J Trop Biomed* 3(5): 337-352
23. Zaoui A, cherrah Y, Macaroni N, Alcohol, Although H, Hassan M. *Acute & chronic toxicity of nigella sativa fixed oil phytomedicine*. 2002;9:69-74
24. <https://nefertiti-eg.com/boost-your-immune-system-with-natural-black-seed-oil/> (accessed) Ansari S.H and Ali M. *Hair Care & herbal drug Indial J Natural product* 13(1): 3-5 1997
25. M.A. Abu-Al- Basal, *Influence of nigella sativa fixed oil on some blood parameters and histopathology of skin in staphylococcal-infected BALB/C mic*. *Biological Science* (2) (2011) PP-1038 1046
26. Omar V. Narule, Manjar D. Kengar, Pranali D. Malik, Sohel I. Nadaf, Bhagyashree A. Mote,

- Trupti D. Dudhagaonkar Formulation and evaluation polyherbal hair oil.
27. Salih H.M. Aljabre, omkar M. Alakloby, Mohammad A Randhawa "journal of Dermatology & dermatologic surgery" published by Elseviews July 2015
 28. Dattner AM., From Medical Herbalism to Phytotherapy in Dermatology: Back to the Future. *Dermatol Ther* 2003; 16(2):106- 113
 29. Huffman MA. . Animal self-medication and Ethno-medicine: exploration and exploitation of the medicinal properties of plants. *Proc Nutr Soc* 2003; 62(2):371 – 81.
 30. Miller KL, Liebowitz RS, Newby LK. Complementary and alternative medicine in cardiovascular disease: a review of biologically based approaches. *Am Heart J* 2004; 147(3): 401 – 11.
 31. Thatte UM, Rege NN, Phatak SD, Dahanukar SA. The Flip Side of Ayurveda. *J Postgrad Med* 2004; 39(4):179–82, 182a–b.
 32. Thatte UM, Kulkarni MR, Dahanukar SA. Immunotherapeutic modification of *Escherichia coli* peritonitis and bacteremia by *Tinospora cordifolia*. *J Postgrad Med* 1992; 38(1): 13 – 5.

HOW TO CITE: Shital Sagale*, Rohit Jadhav, Archana Chavan, Dhananjay Khandebharad, Komal Matsagar, A Review on Formulation and Evaluation of Tetra herbal Hair Oil, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, Vol 3, Issue 5, 4186-4194. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15511498>

